

NATURAL DYE AND ITS APPLICATION ON WOOL IN DIFFERENT MEDIUM

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Abstract

The leaves of Codiaemum Variegatum were dried in shade and was powdered. The powder was refluxed With alcohol for 12 hours, filtered and the solvent was evaporated using rotator apparatus at reduced pressure, the solid obtained as Natural dye was then applied on wool with Alum as mordant in different medium gave different shades.

Key words: Dye, Wool, Natural, Codiaemum Variegatum

Preparation of Natural dye.:-

The shade dried leaves powder of Codiaemum Variegatum was refluxed with alcohol for 12 hours, filtered and the solvent evaporated using rotator apparatus at reduced pressure. The solid Natural dye obtained.

Compounds present in codiaemum Variegatum are

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Compounds present in *Codiaeum variegatum* are :

Pseudopurpin

Purpurin

Primin

Miconidin

Primetin

Pseudopurpin and Purpurin form complex with Alum. When these complexes treated with wool in different medium different shades obtained. 1st dyeing then mordaning in neutral medium with 10% Natural dye and 10% of Alum by boiling for half hour different shades of light brown colour obtained and by increasing the percentage of Alum to 20% and 20% of Natural dye these colour changes to dark. In all cases the neutral medium give light shade whereas in basic medium the colour of the wool dark in comparison to the colour obtained in acidic medium. The colour of wool after dyeing without mordant Alum is different. In neutral medium with 10% of Natural dye give light greenish brown, in acidic medium brown and in basic medium light brown. Whereas in 20 % of Natural dye without mordant in neutral medium gave dark greenish brown, in acidic medium greenish brown and in basic medium it gives brown colour. The colour is dark in neutral medium and become lighter in acidic and basic medium. In all cases after dyeing the wool was washed with water and dried in shade at room temperature.

OBSERVATION AND SHADE CARD.

Colour of wool after Dyeing without mordant:

SL NO	SAMPLE	COMPOSITION (Dye only)	MEDIUM
1		10% Of Dye	Neutral
2		10% Of Dye	Acidic
3		10% Of Dye	Basic
4		20% of Dye	Neutral
5		20% of Dye	Acidic
6		20% of Dye	Basic

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5.1 Observations:

Colour of wool 1st Dyeing then mordanting

SL NO	SAMPLE	COMPOSITION (Dye + Mordant)	MEDIUM
1		10% Of Dye + 10% of Alum	Neutral
2		10% Of Dye + 10% of Alum	Acidic
3		10% Of Dye + 10% of Alum	Basic
4		10% of Dye + 20% of Alum	Neutral
5		10% of Dye + 20% of Alum	Acidic
6		10% of Dye + 20% of Alum	Basic
7		20% of Dye + 10% of Alum	Neutral
8		20% of Dye + 10% of Alum	Acidic
9		20% of Dye + 10% of Alum	Basic
10		20% of Dye + 20% of Alum	Neutral
11		20% of Dye + 20% of Alum	Acidic
12		20% of Dye + 20% of Alum	Basic

Conclusion:- While dyeing with alum in different medium, the wool texture does not change, the wool in neutral medium was soft as compared with in acidic and basic medium.

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